

LOCAL CRAFT PRODUCTION: ANALYSIS OF REVENUE GENERATION STRATEGIES FOR ESSIEN UDIM PEOPLE OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the local craft production as a source of revenue generation for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study's objectives were to examine the roles of local craft as a source of employment, source of livelihood, and as source of income for the Essien Udim people. Three hypotheses were formulated for the study. The structural functional theory was adopted as a theoretical framework. Survey research design with quantitative approaches was adopted for this investigation. A total of 400 questionnaires copies were administered to the study respondents, but a total of 359 respondents returned their questionnaires which were used for analysis. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for testing hypotheses. Analysis of result shows that the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of employment (SOC) for people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.762, p < 0.001$), the Pearson product-moment correlation (r) of local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant at $r = 0.794, p < 0.001$, and the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of income (SOI) for people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.784, p < 0.001$). Meaning that, local craft production in Essien Udim Local Government Area has been a major source of employment for changing the economic status of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. It is a dependable source of livelihood with historical records which is as old as the formation of Essien Udim community. Among others, the researcher recommended that the state government should make investments in local craft production due to its capacity to reduce unemployment among youths, especially in rural areas, and reduce the rural-urban migration among the young age cohorts.

KEYWORDS: Local Craft, Revenue, Livelihood, Employment, and Income

INTRODUCTION

Prior the incursion of Western colonial powers into Africa, which subsequently facilitated the introduction of Western products and technologies, there existed a rich tradition of artisanship among local communities. These artisans crafted tools, equipment, and furniture essential for the sustenance of African populations within their respective environments. Before European influence permeated Nigeria, local craftsmanship had already significantly shaped the technological and artistic landscape of the people (Jayeola-Omoyeni and Omoyeni, 2014). Research conducted by Manabete and Umar in 2014 at Osogbo, Nigeria indicates that Africa is endowed with a wealth of indigenous technologies and knowledge pertinent to local crafts, deeply rooted in the continent's cultural and ecological diversity. For example, various communities across Nigeria, Ghana, Egypt, South Africa, and Sudan, akin to the Aboriginal peoples of Australia, have developed Indigenous technological artefacts, including tools, weapons, nets, baskets, bags, and watercraft such as canoes.

In Nigeria and throughout Africa, these indigenous technologies and knowledge manifest in crafts such as agricultural implements, cooking utensils, weaponry, and construction materials. These technologies and knowledge have served as the foundation of Nigerian society at multiple levels, significantly influencing the region's economy. The study by Manabete and Umar (2014) has demonstrated that the pursuit of Western education has led to the neglect of certain indigenous knowledge systems, resulting in challenges in achieving internal revenue generation. A primary issue contributing to the technological lag in West Africa, and Africa as a whole, is the failure of governments, stakeholders, and the local populace to leverage viable indigenous alternatives found within traditional crafts. Addressing this issue requires recognizing and valuing indigenous technology, granting it the significance and respect it rightfully deserves.

Craft plays a crucial role in the cultural identity and heritage of Nigeria. During prosperous market conditions, it serves as a significant source of income for numerous Nigerian families. Both historically and in present-day rural and urban areas, craft has been a vital contributor to economic activities at local, national, and international levels. It offers direct and indirect employment opportunities for individuals in these regions, thereby enabling many to achieve self-sufficiency (Siyanbola *et al.*, 2012). Indigenous knowledge encompasses the well-established traditions and practices of specific regional indigenous and local communities. Craftspeople typically operate as self-employed individuals, often from their homes, and they generate employment for family members as well as for apprentices and journeymen who are trained in specific crafts. This practice effectively expands the workforce within households (Siyanbola *et al.*, 2012). Craft has been significantly overlooked in national policies aimed at fostering economic development in Nigeria, despite its evident importance. While art and design play a crucial role in shaping both national and global cultural identities, they do not offer the same level of employment opportunities as craft, which focuses on the creation of goods for daily use and consumption. Craft serves as a vessel for tradition and cultural identity, acting as the primary means through which traditional education has preserved the material culture of past civilizations. This form of education encompasses the knowledge, wisdom, and teachings inherent in communities (Manabete and Umar, 2014).

As globalization accelerates, craft faces increasing competition from inexpensive mass produced goods originating from China and India. This detrimental 'race to the bottom' poses a significant threat to many of Nigeria's craftspeople, who often remain unorganized and disempowered. There is an urgent need for strategies and support to ensure that craft can

maintain its vital role in contributing to the cultural and societal fabric of Nigeria. Manabete and Umar (2014) identify a critical issue contributing to the technological lag in West Africa, and more broadly across the African continent, as the failure of governments, stakeholders, and the local populace to leverage viable Indigenous solutions through traditional crafts. Addressing this challenge necessitates recognizing and elevating indigenous technology and craftsmanship to the prominence and respect they warrant.

The concept of revenue generation can be understood in two distinct ways: broadly and narrowly. In its broader interpretation, public income encompasses all forms of income or receipts that a public authority can obtain over a specified timeframe. Conversely, in a narrower interpretation, it refers solely to the income sources of a public authority that are typically recognized as revenue resources. To eliminate any potential confusion, the broader interpretation is referred to as public revenue (Shil, 2019). Prioritizing foreign technologies over these local elements obscures and jeopardizes the community's collective survival, identity, and progress which affects local revenue generation (Manabete and Umar, 2014). In light of Manabete's position, this research aims to explore the role of local crafts in generating revenue for the residents of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State are Annang people known for their stride in local craft production for local use and exportation. Their indigenous knowledge of craft existed even before the arrival of the Europeans and has been persevered and passed from one generation to another as part of their culture. This expertise in local craft has provided the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, and the neighbouring states with house utensils, farm tools, war equipment, furniture, climbing robes, clothing materials, shoes, beads, bags, etc. Their crafts include; shoes, bags, machetes, hoes, pots, spoons, climbing robes, traps, gongs, knives, go-to-hell, chairs, bells, hunters' guns, Jewries, chains, trumpets, drums, etc. According to Essien (2013), these local crafts have enhanced human existence in this part of the world even before the invasion of Africa by the Western world.

The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area had survived on the income generated from the production of the local craft until the invasion of Nigeria by the British. The colonial invasion of Nigeria was executed with the introduction of Western crafts which also influenced the market and the life of the people of Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria as a whole. The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area had found a way of upholding their traditional local craft as a cultural heritage and an adaptive mechanism of the people of the area. The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area have been able to propel the challenge of the Western craft and knowledge into a blessing by the local artisans, who hoped to understand the technology with which the white men employed to produce their kind of utensils, and other equipment. Even though the desire for Western craft or crafts produced through the use of modern technology has grown over time among some Essien Udim people through the influence of the people of the neighbouring local government areas and states, with the building of schools to encourage modern technological knowledge in craft productions and other aspects of life. (Essien, 2013) argued that in Nigeria and Africa, many local artisans send their children to these schools to acquire the Western expertise to incorporate same into the already existed local knowledge for the improvement of their local craft production.

Throughout the colonial era, very little success has been recorded in improving the local knowledge and craft along the European line. The Western knowledge that was supposed to empower the local artisans to improve on their expertise knowledge has over the years, not been successful in line with the aims of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area. Even though Western technological knowledge through Western education was arranged to be able to produce graduates who can go back and take up their parents' local factory and transform such into more a modernized craft production factory, it created a gap between the desire for local crafts and foreign crafts, some of the Essien Udim people have refused to let down or abandoned their local craft heritage.

Today, even though our local markets are filled with foreign products imported from the West and China against the availability of locally produced products by local artisans. Local craft as produced by the Essien Udim people have continually found a competitive place within the local markets both within Essien Udim Local Government Area and in markets outside the local government area. Even though in recent times we tend to produce more graduates through Westernized education who are filled with desires for foreign products against local crafts, many factors still create room for the need for local crafts. Factors like the cost of modern equipment, availability of modern tools in most of the rural areas, traditional cuisines which need local craft for preparation, availability of local craft in local markets for the closeness to the people, affordability of local crafts, easy maintenance of local crafts, and ease-to use of local crafts by the people with low level of education have helped in motivating the local craft productions in the local government area. Local artisans and their families in Essien Udim Local Government Area are finding reasons to continue in production, and to compete in the markets with their local craft products.

The increased and steady presence of local crafts to satisfy the local needs of the people has generated continuous desires for local crafts across the area and other areas of Akwa Ibom State. This scenario has created the importance of local craft as produced by the Essien Udim people. The importance of local crafts has been witnessed in the sustainability of families' economic conditions and livelihoods, as well as in obtaining revenues from local authorities and advancing the cultural heritage of the area's people. These roles have reduced the capacity and chance of foreign products driven by modern technology and Westernized educational knowledge, hindering the advancement of indigenous/local craft knowledge. Though there is a disappearance of subjects that encourage local craft production in the school system today, Essien Udim people are finding ways of incorporating local craft knowledge into their existence as a cultural heritage and means of economic sustainability.

Though there are many works of literature like Essien (2013); Ade (2019) and Baily (2023), on the importance of local crafts in economic development, there is a gap in the roles of the local crafts in revenue generation to the Essien Udim Local Government Area and its people. Despite the economic contribution of local craft to Essien Udim people, reports have been scarce on the functionality of local craft as a source of revenue. The majority of Essien Udim people depend on Local crafts for economic means and livelihood. Against this backdrop, the research sets out to examine the roles of local craft as a source of revenue for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study sought to examined the roles of local craft as a source of economic revenue generation for the Essien Udim people.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the functions of local craft as a source of employment for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area.
2. Investigate the functions of local craft as a source of livelihood for households in Essien Udim Local Government Area
3. Examine the roles of local craft as a dependable source of income for families among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses were considered for testing in the study;

1. Ho: There is no significant relationship between local craft production and employment opportunities for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.
2. Ho: There is no significant relationship between local craft production and means of livelihood of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.
3. Ho: There is no significant relationship between local craft production and income of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Local Craft; Employment, Livelihood, and Income

According to Kpakpakpa (2019), the local crafts industry in Nigeria is diverse with people gaining useful employment and income through making everything from jewelry and furniture to clothing and accessories. According to Iriwieri (2009), arts and crafts are the result of man's desire to improve the world by utilizing nature's benevolence. Nature has made everything tangible and intangible available for man's use and development. The tangible things include trees, grasses, gravel, granite etc. while the intangible is the idea. As such, Arts and Crafts could serve as a springboard for sustainable development and industrialization in a given economy for there seems to be a conscious non awareness of the value, potential and significance of Crafts in everyday life. This is evidenced by people's purchase patterns and positive attitudes towards machine-made products more than man-made objects despite their high standard of workmanship and their durability (Iriwieri, 2009). Iriwieri (2009) further maintained that craft articles possess artistic qualities which enhance their attraction and market value. The local craftsmanship includes cloth weaving, mat-making, pottery, basketry, utility carving, smothery, jewelry etc. according to Iriwieri (2009), these are briefly discussed as follows:

Pottery: It involves molding or hand building of clay objects like utensils, animals and other-shapes. Where possible they are decorated, fired and glazed. Pottery is another occupation dominated by women. Clay is obtained from river banks. It is mixed with water and kneaded sufficiently to enable the potter mold whatever objects is required. The molded object is allowed to dry in the sun for three or more days. It is then sprinkled with water and scraped to become smooth. It is dried in the sun again before being finally baked over an open fire. The potters produce a wide variety of earthen ware including cooking pots bowls, mugs and the traditional Ukoko pipes with a six-foot long bamboo mouth-piece. With the acquisition of kiln and varieties of glaze and potter's wheel, a cottage pottery industry, which will be self-sustaining, can take off. This pottery art is peculiar to the states in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria such as Osun, Ondo, Delta, Bayelsa, Rivers, Imo, Ebonyi amongst others (Iriwieri, 2009). **Weaving:** This embraces a whole gamut of crafts such as making of clothes, baskets, hats, fans, carpet, rug, bags, chairs, mats and other items peculiar to almost all the states in the

six geo-political zones in Nigeria particularly those in the core North and South-south. The materials for production of these articles are derived from raffia fibers, grass, palm fronds and canes among others. For instance; clothes are hand-woven and highly dominated by the women folk who employ the same technique.

Weaving: This is done on a simple loom installed in a corner of the room. The looms usually consist of two wooden poles, each about six feet long planted on the floor, side by side with each other in a slanting position and at a distance of about three feet apart. Two other poles are tied across the standing ones. The first about eighteen inches from the ground and the other about four feet away from the first. This constitutes the basic framework. The yarn is produced by ginning raw cotton on a special type of bow. A mass of cotton is placed over the bow and as the string is pulled in a speedy manner at rapid intervals, the seeds are wrenched from the cotton wool. With a wooden spindle consisting of a long spin and a knob at the base, the wool is spun into a yarn or thread. Lengthy coils of thread are fixed on to the loom and swung round the cross poles to form the base fabric. They are held in required positions by carved sticks, designed for the purpose. Weaving is carried out with the help of a wooden shuttle with two pointed ends. The shuttle is used to shoot the yarn across the warp or fabric to form a weft or web. Patterns are affected by the use of large needles. Coloured threads are obtained from camwood and kolanuts. Generally, the clothes are thick and rather coarse in texture, but lighter and smoother ones are also made. The finished clothes are used for dresses and home furnishing such as door and window blind, bedding, table covers, theatre stage background, curtains, architectural theatrical designs (costume, mask, stage scenery, models and set puppets) among others. Mats are thick and coarse fabric made from the fronds of the raffia palm or the soft tender and glossy kind made from rushes. Plaiting is done mostly on the floor where the mat-maker squats and on the top when certain decorative patterns are to be plaited. Some mats are used as bedding, some as table mats and others as wall mats.

Mat-making is traditionally a woman's occupation. Fans are produced by mat-makers from rushes, while the gorgeous chiefs fan with wooden frills and leather embroidery is made by special craftsmen. Embroidery on plain cloth or other materials with yarn of cotton or silk can also be produced. Baskets are made extensively in the riverine areas. The basic raw materials are obtained from palm fronds and canes. Products include fishing baskets, farmers' wicker baskets, shopping and waste-paper baskets and cane-chairs.

Carving: According to Iriwieri (2009), this is another craft which involves making of patterns on calabashes, wood, slab of clay and cement. Objects produced include wooden ash-trays, stools, chests, walking sticks, candle holders, canoe paddles, ebony rings, ear-rings and carved iroko panelled doors. This is extensively produced in some of the Northern and Southern states such as Sokoto, Kano, Kaduna, Edo, Delta Osun, and Ondo among others. **Blacksmithing:** Iriwieri (2009) further state that the work of blacksmithing provides farmers with cutlasses, and housewives with articles such as kitchen knives and hair-pins, wrought iron gates and window grills. There are gold smiths and silver smiths- who make trinkets, rings and exotic silver jewelry incorporating Nigerian amethyst and other stones. This is prevalent in the Southeastern states such as Anambra, Enugu, Imo, Ebonyi among others.

Leather works: This is another veritable occupation particularly in the northern part of the country where most of the people are engaged in livestock, cattle, goat, and donkey rearing trade amongst other animals. Decoration of leather by printing and sewing on patterns, bags, footwear, wallets, belts, pouffes, dresses, etc. The states where this is predominantly practice include Sokoto, Kano, Kaduna, Borno, Gombe and Taraba (Iriwieri, 2009).

Graphic Arts: Graphic Arts are concerned with the problems of preparing and organizing

visual symbols for the communication of ideas and information and satisfying the needs of the advertising industries (Irivwieri, 2009). Diverse creative graphic art works can readily be established from a very humble beginning with little cost, which in no distant period, create further jobs for the teeming population. Crafts workshops and art studios where some hand and machine crafted articles are produced and sold could be set up. In this area, is book-binding which entails the making of prints into book cover and folders, cutting paper and cloth prints to make jackets and the binding of old and new books. As part of environmental design with wall decorations, walls are decorated with mosaics, beads, collage, broken pottery, reliefs, stained glass, etc.

Graphic Arts is commercial art which span through all the metropolitan cities in Nigeria such as Lagos, Port -Harcourt, Warri, Enugu, Kaduna Kano Abuja among others. During the industrial revolution in Britain, greater considerations were given to both the aesthetic and technological aspects of industrial products. This is a clear demonstration of the strong relationship of Arts and Crafts and Industrial design. However, the above listed and discussed arts and crafts practices if well harnessed will provide a base for developing countries, to set up small scale cottage industries, as spring board for industrial growth and development. This could be done at minimal costs, in terms of material and equipment (Irivwieri, 2009). The notion of authentic and viable cultural resources such as traditional crafts in Nigeria sound like a joke to most Nigerian communities (Okonkwo and Oguamanam, 2013). They are yet to understand the values of these cultural resources as well as the benefits of traditional crafts to the host community. Many Nigerian communities are richly blessed with their own indigenous crafts and industries, which could help them to grapple with their environment and progressively enhance their living (Okonkwo and Oguamanam, 2013).

Among such notable industries/indigenous crafts and communities are the blacksmithing industry in Ogbomoso, Ebiraland, Ihima and Ekpedo communities; palm wine tapping industry in Umundu, Ukehe and Enugu-Ezike, communities/towns; iron smelting/smithing in Opi, Orba, Owerre-Elu, Adiasim and Ijja communities, among others. The basic truth is that no organized society can thrive without indigenous crafts and industries (Okonkwo and Oguamanam, 2013). In Africa and elsewhere, one of the earliest indigenous technologies was the rubbing of stones against each other to produce fire which was used for cooking, lighting and keeping houses warm and comfortable (Abdulkareem, 1992 cited Manabete and Umar, 2014).

Several years before the advent of colonialism in Africa, several indigenous technologies existed in many communities. These LCs included iron smelting in the Old Oyo kingdom, tin smelting around Jos in North-Central Nigeria, artistic bronze works in the Benin Empire and Ife in Southern Nigeria. There was also the local manufacture of Dane guns, cutlasses, hoes and axes by local blacksmiths (Aliyu, 2003). In many communities in Adamawa State, North-Eastern Nigeria, notably the Chamba, Longuda and Higgi peoples, just like the Aboriginal people of Australia, there exist similar tools and implements such as knives, spears, axe heads, hoes, bows and arrows, drinking vessels and catapults (L'kama, Manabete, Kamaunji and Ahmed, 2008).

The work of Amuda, Amuda and Waziri (2012) showed that very many years ago, indigenous technologies and science practices were common among women in Borno State, North-Eastern Nigeria. The practices included using glass mirrors, washing plates and clothes, splitting firewood using the axe-head, treating fever, diarrhea and cough by steaming leaves and other herbs, and applying natural products like ash, ground pepper and animal dung to protect crops against pests and diseases. There have been in existence indigenous industries

in Nigeria and in several parts of West Africa. These indigenous technology industries include the production of pots from clay, and especially the wonder clay pot and stove from Sierra Leone (shown on Go TV in Adamawa State, Nigeria). Others are textile making, cloth weaving, production of aluminum metal scraps and pots, leather tanning and bronze casting. Indigenous leather tanning industries are prominent in Northern Nigeria, notably in Sokoto, Kano, Jigawa, Borno and Zamfara States. The methods of acquisition of these technologies are mostly through apprenticeship, oral transmission and observation (Siyanbola *et al.*, 2012).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Structural Functionalism

Structural-functional theory, commonly known as functionalism, conceptualizes society as a complex system composed of interconnected components that are intended to fulfil the biological and social requirements of its members. This perspective emerged from the works of the English philosopher and biologist Herbert Spencer (1820–1903), who drew parallels between society and the human body. He posited that, similar to how various organs collaborate to maintain the body's functionality, the different elements of society work in concert to ensure its proper operation (Spencer 1898). The 25 components of society that Spencer identified include social institutions, which encompass established patterns of beliefs and behaviours aimed at addressing social needs, such as government, education, family, healthcare, religion, and the economy. In the context of local craft production, it has played a significant role in revenue generation. This indicates that local crafts have emerged as a vital source of income for numerous individuals in the Essien Udim Local Government Area. Furthermore, local crafts have been instrumental in generating revenue for both the communities and the local government area.

METHODOLOGY

This study examines the contributions of local craft in generating revenue for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The researcher employed a survey research design of quantitative approaches for this investigation. In terms of methodology, the design incorporated a sampling strategy, specifically the simple random sampling technique. Consequently, questionnaires were utilized as data collection instruments. Primary data were gathered through the distribution of questionnaires to the study respondents. The questionnaire was meticulously structured to address the research objectives. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Essien Udim Local Government Area was created on the 8th of May, 1989, by the Ibrahim Babangida administration with its headquarters at Afaha Ikot Ebak. The name is a combination of the two former Local Government: Essien Anaang Local Government with its Headquarters at Ikot Obio Okon and UDIM Local Government with its Headquarters at Ukana Iba of Cross River State, Nigeria.

On the creation of Akwa Ibom State, the two Local Government Areas were amalgamated and called Essien Udim. UDIM is an acronym –U= Ukana, D= Adiasim, I= Ikpe Anaang and M= Mkpatak just like INI and ONNA Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State and ABIA and BAYELSA States of Nigeria. Essien Udim people are homogenous. They are of the Annang stock. They are very hospitable, and sociable and practice an extended family system. They are predominantly Christians, but a minority of them practice some form of Traditional African Religion. The area is blessed with arable land that favours oil palm, cassava, and rubber plantations. The area also has a large deposit of ceramic and bricks. The

creative ingenuity of the people is exemplified in the production of raffia bags and shoes, wood carvings, basket making, pottery, blacksmithing, den gongs, hats, mats, local gins, insecticides, and fertilizers. There is also untapped crude in the area (Ibom Yellow Page, 2018). Essien Udim Local Government Area has eleven clans, 28 wards, and 136 villages with a population of 192,668 residents according to the 2006 Census. The projected population of Essien Udim Local Government Area as of 2018 stood at 288,657 according to the data made available by the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower, 2018. This makes Essien Udim one of the largest Local Government Areas in the State.

The study concentrated in Essien Local Government Area; it used a combination of stratified and simple random sampling techniques in the selection of the respondents. In the area, there exist 11 clans and 136 villages. Thus, clans were demarcated so that each clan produced at least 36 respondents from at least 2 villages each from the clans. The random selections were carefully done to have one hundred and seventy (170) men and two hundred and thirty (230) women to be randomly selected without duplication. Data for this study were collected by the researcher who was assisted by two (2) clerical officers as research assistants. The study respondents were contacted in their residences, offices and workshops respectively. To collect the needed data, the researcher and his research assistants first disclosed the objectives of the study to the study respondents and requested their candid responses through questionnaires and personal interviews where necessary.

A total of 400 questionnaires in accordance to the sample size were administered to the study respondents, but a total of 359 respondents turned in their questionnaires. Some of the respondents were interviewed in English and some the questions were interpreted in Annang language to suit their level of educational characteristics. The research assistants were trained on the objective of the study and made to be conversant with the design of the study. The 400 questionnaires copies were shared across randomly selected villages within the 11 clans in the Area. The study respondents were randomly selected from villages and the local government headquarters to fill out the questionnaires. The researcher visited 5 local craft centres which are; climbing robe centre at Ikpe Annang, mortar, pestle and traditional drum centre at Ukana, blacksmith centre at Adiasim, and raffia wood work at Uwa in Essien Udim Local Government Area.

RESULT

Hypotheses 1 Ho: There is no significant relationship between local craft production and employment opportunity for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS was used to test hypothesis 1, which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between local craft production (LCP) and sources of employment (SOC) for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, as presented in the table below.

Table 1: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between Local Craft Production (LCP) and Source of Employment (SOE) for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State

Correlation between Local Craft Production (LCP) and Source of Employment (SOE) (n =359)

		LCP	SOE
LCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.762**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	359	359
SOE	Pearson Correlation	.762**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	359	359

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 above shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between Local Craft Production (LCP) and Source of Employment (SOE) for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Correlation between Local Craft Production (LCP) and Source of Employment (SOE) (n =359) LCP SOE LCP Pearson Correlation 1 .762 ** Sig. (2-tailed) N SOE Pearson Correlation .762 ** 1 Sig. (2-tailed) N **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Table 1 shows that the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of employment (SOE) for people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.762$, $p < 0.001$). Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis one was not supported which states that there is no significant relationship between local craft production and sources of employment for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. This implies that there is a significant relationship between local craft production and sources of employment for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. This shows that the local craft production has been a longtime source of employment for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, who have depended on it as a source of revenue generation for the people in their historical survival within the geographical space known as Essien Udim.

The high positive relationship between the study variables as captured in Hypothesis 1 is indicated by the Pearson product-moment correlation (r) which is +0.762. The rules state a high positive or negative correlation exists when $r = + 0.70$ to $+ 0.90$. In the case of the correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of employment (SOE) for people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) = +0.762 which supports a high positive statistical significance between the two variables (local craft production (LCP) and sources of employment (SOE)), and its statistical significant is lower than 0.01 level of significant at 0.000.

Hypotheses 2 Ho: there is no significant relationship between local craft production and means of livelihood among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was used for testing Hypotheses 2 which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State as presented in the table below;

Table 2: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between local craft production (LCP) and source of livelihood (SOL) ($n = 359$)

		LCP	SOL
LCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.794**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	359	359
SOL	Pearson Correlation	.794**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	359	359

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 above shows that the Pearson product-moment correlation (r) of local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant at $r = 0.794$, $p < 0.001$. Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant relationship between local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was not supported and therefore rejected. This shows that local craft production has been a major source of livelihood through revenue generation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. The implication here is that the majority of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area are depending on local craft production for financial supports for sustainability of their families and their community development projects and programmes.

The high positive relationship between the study variables as captured in hypotheses two is indicated by the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) which is $+0.794$. The rules state that there exists a high positive or negative correlation when $r = +0.70$ to $+0.90$. In the case of the tested hypotheses which stated that there is no significant relationship between local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, the correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, $r = +0.794$ which supports a high positive statistically significant relationship between the two variables and the statistically significant is lower than 0.01 level of significant at .000. Therefore, the tested hypothesis is rejected at null state, and the alternate state is accepted which state that there is a significant relationship between local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypotheses 3 Ho: There is no significant relationship between local craft production and income for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS was used to test hypothesis 3, which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between local craft production (LCP) and dependable sources of income (SOI) for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, as presented in the table below.

Table 3: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between Local Craft Production (LCP) and Source of income (SOI) for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State

Correlation between Local Craft Production (LCP) and Source of Employment (SOC) ($n = 359$)

		LCP	SOI
LCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.784**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	359	359
SOI	Pearson Correlation	.784**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	359	359

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 above shows that the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of income (SOI) for people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.784$, $p < 0.001$). Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis three was not supported which states that there is no significant relationship between local craft production and sources of income for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. This implies a significant relationship between local craft production and sources of income for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. This shows that the local craft production has been a longtime dependable source of income for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, who have depended on it as a source of revenue generation for the many families in their historical survival within the geographical space known as Essien Udim.

The high positive relationship between the study variables as captured in Hypothesis 1 is indicated by the Pearson product-moment correlation (r) which is $+0.784$. The rules state a high positive or negative correlation exists when $r = + 0.70$ to $+ 0.90$. In the case of the correlation (r) between local craft production (LCP) and sources of income (SOI) for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. The Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) = $+0.784$ which supports a high positive statistical significance between the two variables (local craft production (LCP) and sources of income (SOI)), and its statistical significance is lower than 0.01 level of significance at 0.000.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study through the analysis of data collected from the field show that for hypothesis one there exists a highly positive relationship between the local craft production (LCP) and sources of employment (SOE) for people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, it is and statistically significant at Pearson Product-moment Correlation $r = 0.762$, $p < 0.001$. This shows that local craft production in Essien Udim Local Government Area has been a major source of employment for changing generations of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Analysis of findings gathered through

questionnaires revealed that many the people of Essien Udim within the young and old especially of the male gender have been gainfully employed in craft production. This has help the Essien Udim people to create local craft industries which has been a known source of employment for the people. The employment has spread across both the male and female gender. This implies that the local craft production provide employment opportunities for men and women with regards to gender. While men are into craft production, women are marketing the craft in the markets. This finding agrees with Manabete and Umar (2014) who posit that Africa is endowed with a wealth of indigenous technologies and knowledge pertinent to local crafts, deeply rooted in the continent's cultural and ecological diversity. For example, various communities across Nigeria, Ghana, Egypt, South Africa, and Sudan, akin to the Aboriginal peoples of Australia, have developed indigenous technological artefacts, including tools, weapons, nets, baskets, bags, and watercraft such as canoes.

Local craft production has been a dependable source of livelihood with historical records as old as the formation of the Essien Udim community. This was ascertained by the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) of local craft production (LCP) and sources of livelihood (SOL) among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State that was highly positive and statistically significant at $r = 0.794$, $p < 0.001$. Analysis of findings shows that the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area have been living on revenue generated from local craft production and marketing of local craft. Further analysis presented that the local craft has been a sustainable livelihood rooted in the cultural heritage of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Local craft production and marketing have provided the Essien Udim people with proceeds that they have used for the development of their communities.

As a source of livelihood, local craft factories have been inherited from parents by children and some of the factories are owned as family assets by some families across Essien Udim Local Government Area. These findings give credence to Essien (2013) who reported that even though Western technological knowledge through Western education was arranged to be able to produce graduates who can go back and take up their parents' local factory and transform such into more a modernized craft production factory, it created a gap between the desire for local crafts and foreign crafts, some of the Essien Udim people have refused to let down or abandoned their local craft heritage. Local craft production has consistently served as a reliable source of income, with historical documentation tracing back to the establishment of the Essien Udim community. This assertion is supported by the Pearson Product moment Correlation (r) analysis, which indicates a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between local craft production (LCP) and sources of income (SOI) among the residents of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, yielding $r = 0.784$, $p < 0.001$. The analysis reveals that the inhabitants of Essien Udim Local Government Area have relied on income derived from local craft production and the marketing of these crafts.

Further examination indicates that local craft serves as a sustainable livelihood deeply embedded in the cultural heritage of the Essien Udim community. The production and sale of local crafts have enabled families in Essien Udim to generate income essential for their survival. Many local craft enterprises have been passed down from parents to children, with some of these businesses recognized as family assets within various households throughout the area. These findings align with Essien's (2013) observations, which noted that while Western educational systems aimed to equip graduates with the skills to modernize their parents' local craft businesses, a divide emerged between the appreciation for local crafts and

foreign alternatives. Nevertheless, many individuals in Essien Udim have chosen to preserve their local craft traditions rather than abandon them.

CONCLUSION

This study sought to investigate local craft as a source of economic revenue generation for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, in Akwa Ibom State. Local craft production is as old as the historical-cultural setting of the Essien Udim people. As part of adaptation, the Essien Udim people have engaged in local craft production for survival, and this craft production has offered employment to the Essien Udim people from one generation to another. It has been a dependable source of livelihood for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area who have lived on the proceeds from marketing local craft products within and outside the state over many decades.

The local craft factories have served as families' investments and properties across the Essien Udim Local Government Area, and have been inherited from one generation to another. Local craft has its roots in the cultural heritage of the Essien Udim people and has served as a source of employment, livelihood, and income.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made by the researcher for the more successful impact of local craft in Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State;

1. The government should make investments in local craft production due to its capacity to reduce unemployment among youths, especially in rural areas, and reduce the rural-urban migration among the young age cohorts.
2. There should be grants for the local craft producers who have lived on the proceeds of the local craft productions for sustainable production.
3. The Essien Udim Local Government Council should see how to create a local craft market in the Essien Udim Local Government Area to promote the marketing of local craft. To help in the generation of more income for the various families.

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